

EFFECT OF DINING EXPERIENCE ON REVISIT INTENTION TO EXCLUSIVE BARS: MEDIATING ROLE OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of factors influencing dining experience on customers' revisit intention to bars in the hospitality industry with customer satisfaction as a mediator in the garden city of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. A well structured questionnaire containing 18 items, was used to elicit data from from 100 customers who patronise exclusive bars in the high brow Government Reserve Area (GRA) of Port Harcourt. The data gathered was utilised to validate the model developed for the study empirically through statistical tests with the help of SPSS. The inferential statistical analysis revealed that revisit intention to the bars is driven by bar environment, food quality and service quality. The mediating role of customer satisfaction also exists significantly between dining experience and revisit intention. The authors recommend that investors operating bars in the hospitality industry should concentrate on developing cosy bar environment, food quality and service quality. This will enhance customer satisfaction which is capable of promoting customers' revisit intentions, and improve the overall firm performance for the exclusive bars.